

Design and Implementation of a Blockchain-based Donation DApp for Transparent Charity Transactions

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Abstract—This paper presents the development of an interactive web platform designed to bring transparency and trust to charitable giving through the use of blockchain technology. This DApp integrates both Web2 and Web3 components: Here organizations create verified charity campaigns so that donors contribute directly through MetaMask a cryptocurrency wallet, with all transactions immutably recorded on the blockchain for public auditability. The backend (Web2) manages user data, campaign verification, and document storage, enforcing legitimacy through decentralized storage (IPFS). Also with the use of web2 has helped to create a more user friendly and attractive user interface layouts. Ethereum Smart contracts are used for handling, releasing donations based on predefined conditions. A Merkle Tree algorithm is implemented to provide cryptographic proof for donation inclusion in the charities. This platform solves common challenges of traditional charity systems, such as mismanagement, high intermediary fees, and mainly donor mistrust, by offering a secure, decentralized, and automated donation ecosystem.

Index Terms—Blockchain, Smart Contracts, Decentralized Application, Ethereum, Transparency, Donations, MetaMask, IPFS

I. INTRODUCTION

Charity addresses various significant global issues that affect humanity, civilization, and progress. These topics are of great significance and should not be undervalued in any respect [1]. However, numerous conventional donation methods have failed in various aspects. They exhibit a lack of transparency or mishandle finances, imposing high fees via intermediaries, and showing a perceived low degree of accountability from donors. Blockchain technology is highly effective in addressing these challenges by providing a distributed ledger for improving traceability and transparency of donations [2], [3].

This paper introduces a decentralized donation platform that makes use of all of this new technology to create a very secure, transparent, and decentralized donation tracking system. The platform uses smart contracts to bring real transparency to existing defects of the traditional donation system and have

them deployed in a blockchain network so that it cannot be tampered with or edited, coupling wallet linkage, event tracking, and immutably storing data with InterPlanetary File System (IPFS).

II. RELATED WORK

Recently, a number of blockchain-based charity platforms like GiveTrack and Binance Charity have started to pop up that demonstrated the use of blockchain to increase transparency in charitable activities [3]. While these systems claim to provide transparency, they often struggle with issues related to usability and scalability. One significant drawback is the lack of a straightforward way to give or receive donations. This absence makes it challenging to track how donations are transferred from the donor to those in need, creating a gap in visibility. Moreover, many other companies involved in the process tend to introduce extra costs that prolong the transaction, making it even harder for donors to keep an eye on how their contributions are utilized. As a result, these systems risk becoming susceptible to fraud, theft, or misuse, which ultimately diminishes donor confidence and can lead to a decline in future charitable giving. To address these challenges, we propose a user-friendly decentralized application (DApp) that streamlines user interactions and enhances traceability in every transaction.

III. SYSTEM DESIGN

The system architecture has taken an object-oriented approach in system design to model the structure and behaviors of their application. The architecture is modular, with basic components:

- **Frontend Interface:** User-facing modules that is made in next js which runs locally at <http://localhost:3000>. It handles campaign creation, donation flows, tracking, and user profiles and is integrated with metamask. Charity

creator creates charity donor gives donations and admin verifies the charities on chain.

- **Backend Api:** Made in Django that runs locally at <http://localhost:8000>. Handles authentication, campaign management, donation recording, document verification, admin operation of verifying charities off chain and provides implementation of merkle module.
- **Smart Contract Module:** Written in Solidity and deployed on the Ethereum testnet to manage blockchain-based donation processing and campaign verification. The core logic of the dapp that handles all the campaign creation and donation flow logic. Deployed at local JSON-RPC node at <http://localhost:8545>.
- **Decentralized Storage(IPFS):** Stores campaign documents securely and provides public access links. A peer-to-peer technology that ensures decentralized availability of campaign documents. Files are split into blocks, hashed using a Merkle-DAG structure, and retrieved via their cryptographic content identifiers (CIDs), enabling tamper-evident storage and globally distributable public access [5].

Fig. 1. An overall system architecture of the dApp showing the interactions between the major components of the app.

Algorithm Details

This platform uses the following algorithms for secure and transparent donations:

- **SHA-256 Hashing:** The SHA-256 hashing algorithm is used for data integrity and security within the Merkle

Tree. It produces a 256-bit fixed-length hash value, which is computationally infeasible to reverse-engineer or tamper with.

In the context of a Merkle Tree, SHA-256 is applied to hash individual donation records to form leaf nodes. Pairs of nodes are concatenated and hashed again using SHA-256 to form parent nodes, and this process continues until the final Merkle Root is obtained.

The hashing process is defined as:

$$h = \text{SHA256}(x) \quad (1)$$

where x is the input data, and h is the resulting 256-bit hash. This ensures that each node in the Merkle Tree is represented in a unique and tamper-proof manner.

- **Merkle Tree Algorithm:** A Merkle Tree is a binary tree structure used for efficient and secure verification of data integrity. It provides a cryptographic proof that a donation inclusion in the overall set of donations without revealing the entire database [4].

Data Preparation: Let the set of donations be:

$$D = \{d_1, d_2, \dots, d_n\}$$

Each donation d_i is first converted into a standardized string representation. This format is defined as:

$$\text{donation_string} = \text{"id:donor_address:amount:timestamp:tx_hash"}$$

Thus, the set of donation strings is:

$$S = \{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n\}$$

Each string s_i is then hashed using SHA-256:

$$L_i = H(s_i)$$

where $H(x)$ denotes SHA-256, and L_i represents the leaf node in the Merkle Tree.

Tree Construction:

- **Leaf Nodes:** The bottom layer of the tree consists of all donation hashes:

$$L_1, L_2, \dots, L_n$$

- **Parent Nodes:** Each pair of consecutive child nodes is concatenated and hashed to form a parent node:

$$P_j = H(L_{2j-1} || L_{2j})$$

where $||$ denotes string concatenation.

- **Odd Node Handling:** If the number of nodes at any level is odd, the last node is duplicated before hashing:

$$P_j = H(L_{\text{last}} || L_{\text{last}})$$

- **Merkle Root:** The final single hash at the top of the tree is called the Merkle Root:

$$R = \text{MerkleRoot}(D)$$

The Merkle Root uniquely represents the set of all donations.

Proof Generation: To prove that a donation d_k is included in the tree:

- 1) Compute its leaf hash: $L_k = H(d_k)$
- 2) Collect all sibling hashes along the path from L_k to the root.

The proof is a sequence:

$$S = [s_1, s_2, \dots, s_m]$$

where each s_i is a sibling hash at a particular level in the tree.

Proof Verification: Given L_k , the proof sequence S , and the Merkle Root R :

The verification proceeds as follows:

$$h_1 = \begin{cases} H(L_k || s_1), & \text{if } L_k \text{ is a left child} \\ H(s_1 || L_k), & \text{if } L_k \text{ is a right child} \end{cases}$$

$$h_2 = \begin{cases} H(h_1 || s_2), & \text{if } h_1 \text{ is a left child} \\ H(s_2 || h_1), & \text{if } h_1 \text{ is a right child} \end{cases}$$

The process continues iteratively until:

$$h_m = \begin{cases} H(h_{m-1} || s_m), & \text{if } h_{m-1} \text{ is a left child} \\ H(s_m || h_{m-1}), & \text{if } h_{m-1} \text{ is a right child} \end{cases}$$

Finally, if $h_m = R$, where R is the Merkle Root of the donation set, the proof is valid and confirms that d_k is included in the tree.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

The implementation section translates the architectural components into a fully functional decentralized application. Unlike the System Design section, which focused on the logical architecture, this section gives details about the concrete technologies, development environment, and integration workflow used to build the platform.

A. Smart Contract Layer

The smart contracts were implemented in Solidity (v0.8.19) and compiled and deployed using the Hardhat framework. Hardhat's local Ethereum node was used for block mining, event inspection's, and contract-level debugging. The CharityPlatform contract exposes functions for campaign creation, donation processing, and event logging, and emits transaction metadata consumed by the backend.

B. Frontend Implementation

The client-facing dApp was built using Next.js (v14) with server-side rendering. MetaMask integration and blockchain interactions were handled using Ethers.js (v5), enabling account management, transaction signing, and charity activities of creating and donating. Metamask wallet signed the transactions and is the sole medium for paying gas and transactions fee. It communicated with the exposed JSON-RPC node of the local hardhat network. Tailwind CSS was used for component

styling and responsive layout generation. The frontend communicates with:

- the Web3 provider for on-chain logic, and
- the Django backend for off-chain verification metadata.

C. Backend Implementation

The backend was implemented in Django (v4.x), using Django ORM for relational data persistence. A RESTful API layer was developed to manage authentication, off-chain campaign verification, donation metadata, and Merkle proof generation. All donation records were normalized before being inserted into the Merkle module, which computes the Merkle Root and generates inclusion proofs.

SQLite was used during development for lightweight, file-based persistence for charities metadata.

D. Decentralized Storage Integration

IPFS was integrated through an HTTP-based client interface for pinning and retrieving campaign verification documents. Each file is chunked and stored as a content-addressed object within a Merkle-DAG structure, and the backend maintained only the corresponding Content Identifier (CID) rather than the file itself [5]. This enabled tamper free retrieval, ensuring immutability, and decouples document storage from centralized infrastructure. For client access, the CID was serialized into a gateway-resolvable URL of the form `https://gateway.pinata.cloud/ipfs/<CID>`, which allowed the frontend to retrieve the document directly from the distributed network.

E. End-to-End Workflow

A complete workflow includes:

- 1) User interacts with the dApp through the React/Next.js frontend and triggers a transaction.
- 2) MetaMask wallet prompts user to sign the transaction.
- 3) Ethers.js signs and broadcasts the transaction to hardhat local network.
- 4) Smart contract executes the transaction and emits structured events (CharityCreated, DonationMade, CharityVerified).
- 5) Frontend waits for transaction confirmation and retrieves the transaction hash.
- 6) Frontend calls Django backend API to update the database with transaction details.
- 7) Backend stores charity/donation information and associated IPFS document hashes (CIDs).
- 8) Merkle tree generation for batched transaction verification.
- 9) Downloadable cryptographic proofs for donation verification.

This end-to-end integration ensures traceability, transparency, and secure interaction between all system layers.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During unit testing and system level testing, the operation of the platform as well as its integrity were found to be functioning satisfactorily. Backend functionality spanning both the Django backend that was built and smart-contract interfacing versus major process flows User registration, Charity campaign creation, donation management.

It was noticed that normal operation at the frontend delivered all the results that were expected, with some occasional glitches at a few transaction confirmations due to some delay on HardHat underlay test network of blockchain. Except these, the decentralized application performance was fully guaranteed.

TABLE I
GAS CONSUMPTION FOR CORE SMART CONTRACT OPERATIONS

Function	Gas Used	ETH (20 gwei)
Contract Deployment	2,345,261	0.046905
Create Charity (1st)	327,899	0.006558
Create Charity (2nd)	327,935	0.006559
Create Charity (3rd)	327,911	0.006558
Verify Charity	32,684	0.000654
Donate 0.1 ETH	287,703	0.005754
Donate 0.5 ETH	298,728	0.005975
Donate 1 ETH	367,912	0.007358
Donate 10 ETH	270,663	0.005413
Donate 50 ETH	236,523	0.004730
Donate 100 ETH	268,199	0.005364
Donate 5 ETH (repeat)	233,975	0.004680
getCharity (view)	50,962	0.001019
getUserCharities (view)	26,585	0.000532
getUserDonations (view)	31,096	0.000622
getTotalCharities (view)	23,547	0.000471

The gas consumption values presented in Table 1 presents the computational cost of each core operation executed on the Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM). The design of the smart contracts greatly affects the gas consumption patterns [6]. Deployment of contract exhibits the highest cost due to the initialization of storage variables and bytecode provisioning, whereas view functions exhibit lower costs as they do not mutate contract state. Donation-related operations show moderate gas usage because they involve event emission and updates to multiple storage slots.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper presented the design and implementation of a decentralized charity donation platform that addresses key issues of traditional fundraising systems by ensuring transparency, accountability, and traceability of funds. The prototype integrates blockchain technology, smart contracts, IPFS for decentralized storage, and MetaMask-based authentication to create a secure and tamper-proof environment for charitable transactions.

Core functionalities such as campaign creation, smart contract deployment, real-time donation tracking, and document verification were successfully implemented. Despite being developed under academic constraints, the project demonstrated the practical feasibility of blockchain for real-world applications in the non-profit sector.

Fig. 2. Visualization of Gas Consumption for different Smart Contract Operations.

Future Work

Future enhancements aim to improve the scalability, usability, and adoption of the platform. As the paper only presented the development of the dapps in the local level we can adopt and enhance it accordingly in future use.

- **Scalability and Mainnet Deployment:** The system can be deployed on Ethereum mainnet or scalable alternatives such as Polygon or Binance Smart Chain to handle higher transaction volumes at reduced gas costs.
- **Enhanced User Experience:** Develop a more responsive mobile interface or dedicated mobile application, and include multilingual support to engage a global user base.
- **Advanced Security Features:** Integrate multi-signature wallets for fund withdrawals and implement KYC/AML verification to ensure trust and compliance.
- **Stablecoin and Multi-Currency Support:** Enable donations in stablecoins (e.g., USDT) and multiple cryptocurrencies to minimize volatility and expand donor participation.

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